

Work Package 1

Crossing boundaries: A framework for impact and collaborative redesign of school and teacher education

Deliverable 1.2

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Glossary of key terms

This glossary provides brief definitions of important terms used throughout the PhysEd-Academy Framework. It is designed to support shared language and understanding across diverse contexts and professional backgrounds.

Term	Definition
Pre-service teachers	Teachers enrolled in teacher education programs who have not yet entered the profession. They are preparing to be in-service teachers.
In-service teachers	Teachers who are currently working in schools (e.g., primary, secondary, vocational) who are not employed as teacher educators in higher education.
Teacher educators	Teachers (often in universities or training institutions) who prepare, support, and develop teachers through formal education and professional learning.
Teachers	Generally used to refer to professionals – including pre-service teachers, in-service teachers, and teacher educators – who facilitate learning by planning and teaching educational experiences for learners.
Initial Teacher Education (ITE)	Formal undergraduate education that individuals undertake to qualifying as teachers.
Continuous Professional Development (CPD)	Ongoing learning activities for teachers and educators aimed at enhancing skills, knowledge, and practice throughout their careers.
Collective action	A collaborative approach to educational change that involves multiple stakeholder (e.g., pre-service teachers, in-service teachers, and teacher educators) working together across borders.
Cross-border collaboration	Cooperative work across national, institutional, and sectoral boundaries—linking schools, universities, and/or policy actors to share practices, co-create knowledge, and address common educational challenges.
Co-creation	A collaborative process in which multiple stakeholders—such as teachers, teacher educators, students, and policymakers—jointly develop knowledge, practices, or solutions. Co-creation emphasizes shared ownership, mutual learning, and respect for diverse expertise, going beyond consultation or feedback by actively involving all participants.
Communities of Practice (CoPs)	Groups of practitioners (e.g., in-service teachers and teacher educators) who engage in shared learning and inquiry, often over time, to improve professional practice.
Signature pedagogies	Core teaching methods or pedagogies used by teacher in ITE and CPD.
Practitioner inquiry	A method where teachers systematically investigate their own practice to improve teaching and learning.

Executive summary

PhysEd-Academy is an Erasmus+ Teacher Academies-funded project that aims to advance the quality, relevance, and impact of schooling through innovation in teacher education. Rooted in cross-border collaboration and co-creation processes among teacher educators, in-service teachers, and pre-service teachers across multiple countries, the project addresses an urgent challenge: the siloed and fragmented nature of both schooling and teacher education.

Purpose of the Framework

The *PhysEd-Academy Framework* provides a structured yet adaptable guide for transforming teacher education across the continuum – from ITE to CPD. While grounded in the context of physical education, the framework is designed to be applicable and adaptable to all teacher education programs across disciplines. In so doing, it articulates a shared vision for high-quality, inclusive, and future-oriented teacher education, and offers tools and principles to support the development of sustainable teaching cultures that are both evidence-informed and socially responsive.

Target Audience

This framework is intended for:

- Teacher educators engaged in the design and teaching in ITE and CPD.
- CPD providers supporting teacher learning and development across career stages.
- Teacher educators and in-service teachers seeking to engage in self-initiated CPD
- In-service teachers who supervise and pre-service teachers during school placement
- Schools, teacher education institutions, and their leaders aiming to foster innovative, reflective, and collaborative teaching cultures.
- Policymakers, researchers, and curriculum developers involved in education reform and the development of teacher education standards.

Core Strands of the Framework

1. Collective Action

This strand introduces a methodology for educational change grounded in cross-border collaboration and co-creation. Through a combination of CoPs – national and/or international, small and/or large – and practitioner inquiry, the framework supports bottom-up innovation that is sustainable, context-sensitive, and scalable.

2. Signature Pedagogies

This strand defines and categorizes the pedagogies that are central to preparing and supporting both ITE and the CPD of in-service teachers and teacher educators. These include (auto)biographical pedagogies, experiential pedagogies, and pedagogies of professional learning. Each plays a key role in fostering reflective, confident, and collaborative teachers who are equipped to meet the demands of contemporary educational contexts.

Why it matters?

The PhysEd-Academy framework matters because:

- **It helps to bridge the gap between practice, research, and policy**
The framework creates a shared space where teachers, researchers, and policymakers can co-develop solutions, shared language, mutual understanding, and aligned practices. This collaboration enhance the relevance, legitimacy, and uptake of educational innovation.
- **It fosters the link between schools and teacher education**
By fostering structured collaboration between schools and teacher education contexts, the framework ensures that professional learning is relevant, responsive, and rooted in real-world teaching contexts.
- **It offers a scalable model for educational improvement**
The framework supports adaptable and repeatable practices that can be applied across disciplines and countries, enabling meaningful reform beyond isolated projects or pilot programs.
- **It builds capacity for equity-driven change**
In a time of urgent social and environmental challenges, the framework provides an inclusive and flexible infrastructure for evidence-informed, values-based development, offering a shared language for sustainable change.

Introduction

The PhysEd-Academy Framework is a practical tool designed for teachers and other stakeholders to address the key challenges in teacher education across disciplines. It responds to the fragmentation, siloed practices, and a lack of a shared pedagogical language – challenges that affect not only physical education teacher education but teacher education more broadly across Europe. This framework offers a flexible and scalable guide that supports more coherent, collaborative, and responsive approaches to teacher education, making it relevant across subject areas and professional contexts.

PhysEd-Academy is a European Teacher Academy established under Erasmus+ to lead the revitalization of physical education across Europe. It responds to a critical reality: while physical education has unique potential to foster young people's lifelong health, well-being, and agency, its current practices often fail to meet this promise. Outdated and fragmented curricula and teaching traditions leave many young people underprepared to navigate the physical, mental, and social health challenges of the 21st century.

At the same time, the literature highlights that these challenges are not unique to physical education. Across disciplines, teacher education suffers from a lack of shared vision and practices, disconnected phases of CPD, and limited collaboration between schools, universities, and policymakers.

PhysEd-Academy framework invites teachers, leaders and policymakers to take action – reimagining the quality and coherence of teacher education—from ITE through to CPD. It focuses on two key areas: a) bridging the divide between schools and teacher education institutions, and b) integrating more evidence-based pedagogies. By doing so, the framework supports meaningful improvements in the purposes, content, and practices that shape teacher education and strengthen alignment both within teacher education and between teacher education and schooling.

Co-created by physical education teacher educators, researchers, and both pre-service and in-service teachers across multiple European countries, the framework embodies a shared commitment to educational quality, equity, and wellbeing. It is grounded in practical experience and designed for real-world use.

At its core, the framework is built around two interdependent strands that work together to build sustainable, evidence-informed teaching cultures:

- A methodology of collective action—enabling schools, universities and policymakers to co-design, test, and scale innovations that enhance both teacher development and student learning.
- A set of signature pedagogies—defining key teaching practices in teacher education, relevant for both ITE and CPD, and supporting the development of reflective, confident, and collaborative teachers.

The *PhysEd-Academy Framework* contributes to a growing European and global conversation about high-quality teacher education. While developed through the lens of physical education, its principles and practices are transferable across school subjects and teacher education contexts – offering a valuable model for building more connected, inclusive, and future-oriented approaches to teaching and learning.

Key Strands

Collective Action

The **PhysEd-Academy Framework** puts collective action at the centre of meaningful educational change. It offers a practical methodology that teachers, leaders, and policymakers can use to create sustainable, inclusive, and high-impact improvements in their own settings. While many educational reforms remain top-down or disconnected from the realities of teaching, this framework starts with a different assumption: transformation happens when people **learn, lead, and act together**.

Collective action is more than collaboration¹. It's a **strengths-based, solution-focused, and culturally responsive** approach that brings together individuals and institutions across schools, universities, sectors, and countries. When stakeholders (e.g., in-service teachers and teacher educators) work as partners—co-creating professional knowledge, building trust, and driving shared innovation—they lay the foundation for a more relevant and equitable future for education.

This strand gives educators a way to make that happen. It introduces the **core design elements** that supports collective action, then explores how to use **practitioner inquiry** and **communities of practice**, which together form the methodological foundation for collective action. Next, it shares a practical example of a **three-layered CoP structure** develop trough the PhysEd-Academy project. The section also addresses **key challenges** and offers **practical tips** for supporting national and international collaboration. Finally, it concludes by reflecting on **why collective action matters** for the future of teacher education.

Core design elements

To support educators in taking collective action, the framework offers three interrelated strategies². These can be applied to local, national, or international context.

1. International-Comparative Analysis

Cross-border exchange opens up new perspectives. Comparing challenges, practices, and innovations across contexts helps educators recognize common needs and spark

¹ (e.g., Lawson et al., 2021; Beddoes & Jones, 2022; MacPhail & Lawson, 2021)

² MacPhail & Lawson (2021)

fresh thinking. This comparative lens supports more relevant, adaptable, and future-oriented teacher education.

2. **Strategic Partnerships Between Schools and Teacher Education Institutions**

Stronger partnerships between schools and teacher education institutions create feedback loops between practice, research, and policy. These relationships should be co-designed to support mutual learning, shared responsibility, and collective growth, moving beyond hierarchical or one-way models.

3. **Knowledge-Generating Teams**

Interdisciplinary teams—e.g., made up of pre-service teachers, in-service teachers, and teacher educators—create powerful spaces for experimentation and learning. These teams serve as living laboratories where participants can reflect together, try out new ideas, and build professional knowledge that's rooted in real-world practice.

Practitioner inquiry & Communities of practice

Practitioner inquiry³ and **communities of practice (CoPs)**⁴ offer a strong foundation for driving high-quality collective action. Together, they empower participants to act as both practitioners and researchers – exploring their own contexts while engaging in dynamic, multi-layered learning communities.

Practitioner inquiry provides:

- A systematic and flexible process for exploring key pedagogical challenges
- A reflective stance that bridges the gap between research and practice
- A shared professional language grounded in experience, evidence, and context

CoPs ensure:

- Ongoing collaboration through layered participation structures
- Safe spaces for sharing, testing, and refining innovative practices
- A scalable model that ranged from small local teams to a large international network

Together, practitioner inquiry and CoPs create a living ecosystem for professional learning – where participants can improve their practice while contributing to larger, system-level change.

³ (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 2009)

⁴ (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger-Trayner & Wenger-Trayner, 2015)

A three-layered community of practice structure

In the PhysEd-Academy project, collective action took shape through a three layered of CoP-model (illustrated in Figure 1). This model can serve as inspiration for designing similar structures tailored to different goals and partnerships.

1. **A large international CoP**

This network brought together teacher educators, in-service teachers, and pre-service teachers across multiple countries. It provided a space for strategic dialogue, comparative analysis, sharing insights, and co-developing tools and concepts.

2. **Three small international CoPs**

These groups focused on deep exploration of signature pedagogies. Teacher educators reflected on and discussed local experiences of designing and testing these pedagogies across diverse teacher education contexts.

3. **Six local CoPs**

Situated within specific national or regional contexts, these communities brought together in-service teachers and teacher educators to co-design, test, and reflect on pedagogical innovations directly in schools.

Figure 1: PhysEd-Academy collective action approach

Challenges and tips for collective action

Collective action offers a powerful approach to transforming teacher education – but working across countries, institutions, and sectors also brings complexity. Building shared knowledge, practices, and trust across diverse contexts requires intentional effort and strategy. Below, we outline common challenges and provide practical tips to support effective collaboration in diverse educational settings.

Key challenges

- **Cultural differences:** Varied education systems, institutional norms, teaching cultures, and expectations can lead to misunderstandings.
- **Communication barriers:** Differences in language, terminology, and/or academic discourse can slow down progress and impact clarity.
- **Power dynamics:** Hierarchies and unequal participation can limit collaboration.
- **Limited time together:** Distance and/or time zones can limit (face-to-face) interaction and make it harder to build strong relationships.
- **Energy fatigue:** Innovation work is demanding – it requires sustained focus and emotional commitment.

Tips for success

- **Start with shared values and co-create goals:** Begin by clarifying what matters to the group, why the work is important, and how success will be defined. Revisiting these touchstones throughout the action to maintain coherence and motivation.
- **Prioritize safe and trusting spaces:** Make space for vulnerability, uncertainty, and disagreement. Meaningful dialogue is only possible when participants feel respected and heard – especially across languages, cultures, and institutional roles.
- **Embed relational time into the work:** Strong relationships are the foundation of strong collective action. Create opportunities to connect informally, reflect together, and celebrate small wins along the way.
- **Design for layered participation:** Recognizing that participants may contribute in different ways at different times. Create flexible structures that allow varied levels of engagement based on roles, capacities, and contexts.
- **Name and nurture attitude, predisposition, and energy:** Sustainable collaboration requires more than formal commitment – it needs curiosity, enthusiasm, and the emotional energy to support one another's learning and growth.

By proactively addressing these challenges, collective action becomes not only possible but truly transformative – fostering school and teacher education cultures that are collaborative, adaptive, and globally informed.

Why it matters

The PhysEd-Academy collective action approach offers more than a way to improve physical education. It provides a scalable and transferable model that teacher educators, in-service teachers, policymakers, and other stakeholders across disciplines can use to redesign school and teacher education.

By centring structured cross-border collaboration, co-design, and systematic inquiry, this approach turns school and teacher education into a space for collaborative, active improvement – where teacher educators and in-service teachers lead change rather than simply respond to it, working in partnership with others to improve both schooling and teacher education.

In a world facing urgent social, environmental, and health challenges, teacher education must become more responsive, inclusive, and future-oriented. Collective action gives teachers, schools, and institutions the tools to make that shift—together.

Signature Pedagogies

The second strand of the PhysEd-Academy project equips teachers with a practical set of 'Signature pedagogies' – the characteristic forms of teaching that shape how teachers are prepared and supported throughout their careers. This section begins by introducing the **concept of signature pedagogies** and their significance in teacher education, responding to the question 'what are signature pedagogies?'. It then outlines the **core signature pedagogies identified** through the PhysEd-Academy project – each illustrated with real examples from practice. The section concludes by highlighting **why these pedagogies matter**.

What are Signature Pedagogies?

Signature pedagogies are the distinctive ways professionals are taught to think, act, and reflect in their field⁵. In teacher education – across both ITE and CPD – they are the forms of teaching that come to mind when thinking about how teachers are prepared and supported throughout their careers.

Instead of offering a one-size-fits-all approach, signature pedagogies provide a shared foundation and professional language that teacher educators can draw on—and adapt—to meet the needs of their learners and contexts. In recent years, scholars have pointed to the importance of identifying signature pedagogies of teacher education^{6,7}, as doing so helps build a common knowledge base, strengthen program coherence, and support more purposeful pedagogical decision-making across both ITE and CPD.

Curious to learn more? Check out our webpage:

<https://www.physed-academy.com/resource/signature-pedagogies-scoping-review/>

Core Signature Pedagogies Identified

Building on the work of Hordvik and Beni (2024) and shaped by practitioner inquiry throughout the PhysEd-Academy project, this framework proposes three interrelated categories of signature pedagogies to support a shared language and practice across teacher education contexts:

1. **(Auto)biographical Pedagogies**

These pedagogies use on storytelling, self-reflection, and critical dialogue to help learners engage with personal and professional narratives—e.g., vision documents, life histories, and vignettes—to surface tacit beliefs and understand the evolution of pedagogical identities.

⁵ ([Shulman, 2005](#))

⁶ ([O'Sullivan, 2018](#))

⁷ ([Parker et al., 2016](#))

2. **Experiential Pedagogies**

These pedagogies involve immersive, embodied learning opportunities in authentic contexts. Examples include school placements, peer teaching, and “living the curriculum” approaches. These pedagogies prioritize learning by doing, often situated in real-time practice and guided reflection.

3. **Pedagogies of Professional Learning**

These pedagogies foster inquiry, collaboration, and co-construction of knowledge in groups with shared professional goals. Drawing from models such as CoPs and action/practitioner research, these pedagogies create spaces for collective reflection and innovation.

Figure 2 illustrates the three categories of signature pedagogies and specific examples of different forms they may take. These are further elaborated in Table 1, where we also unpack the surface, deep and implicit structure of each of the three signature pedagogies.

Figure 2. PhysEd-Academy signature pedagogies and examples of each

SIGNATURE PEDAGOGY	SURFACE STRUCTURE	DEEP STRUCTURE	IMPLICIT STRUCTURE
(AUTO) BIOGRAPHICAL PEDAGOGIES	Teachers engage with and reflect on real or created stories, experiences, and situations - either their own or those of others - which may be based in the past, present, or future. This may take the form of one or more various reflective techniques (e.g., storytelling, vignettes, written reflections) in a variety of formats (e.g., text, video, audio, photos, artifacts).	Teachers develop the ability to think critically and reflexively and to be sensitive to their own and others' experiences as they both challenge and develop their beliefs about teaching and learning.	Leads to the disruption of taken-for-granted ways of thinking and empowers teachers to advocate for change and an ideal vision for the future of PE, both in their own practices and more broadly in the field.
EXPERIENTIAL PEDAGOGIES	Teachers learn through bodily and lived teaching-learning experiences, in authentic settings, as both teachers and learners. Teachers reflect on and discuss their own and others' teaching-learning experiences.	Teachers develop pedagogical skills and confidence for teaching in diverse settings and with various populations, helping to bridge the theory-practice gap.	Leads to the challenging of teachers' values and beliefs about teaching and learning and assumptions about students' individual needs. Develops sensitivity to the complex nature of teaching-learning and the diversity of learners. Allows teachers to begin to form their professional identity.
PEDAGOGIES OF PROFESSIONAL LEARNING	Teachers collaborate in a pair or group with a shared vision and goal to improve and better understand their practice(s)	Allows for engaged interaction and reflection for teachers to develop the self for professional growth in a safe, collective, and supporting environment.	Teachers learn the ethical and moral responsibility and disposition to become a better teacher and be part of a community.

Table 1. Identification of the three signature pedagogies' surface, deep, and implicit structure

Case studies – examples in practice

To see how these can be used in practice, check out the case studies we have developed for each example of the different forms they can take (see Annex 1). For each case, you will find a brief contextualization and three guiding questions—each linked to a structure of the signature pedagogy. You can see an example of a case below:

CASE 1: Learning Through Self-Study

I've been teaching physical education for a while now, and like many teachers, I want to keep getting better. Recently, I found myself really curious about one specific part of my teaching practice. I wasn't sure where to start, but I'd heard about something called self-study. As I understand it, it's basically taking time to reflect on my own teaching in a structured way. It sounded manageable, so I decided to give it a go.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

This is what it actually looks like in my day-to-day practice:

1. I set a goal for improvement, asking myself: "what do I want to explore?"
2. I invite a trusted colleague to observe a few of my lessons.
3. I make short reflections after teaching—either by jotting down notes or doing a quick voice recording on my phone while heading home.
4. My colleague and I meet informally to talk about what we noticed and learned.
5. I also share some of these reflections with my department during our meetings, so we can all learn from each other.

Looking ahead, I'm planning to bring in student voices, between steps 3 and 4. I want to hear how they experience my lessons. Nothing complex, just quick, anonymous exit slips with simple prompts like: "What I liked most today was... because...", "What I liked least today was... because..." Later, I might even organize group interviews with students, led by another teacher, to dig a little deeper.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

More than anything, this process has helped me pause and think about my practice. It's pushed me to ask questions I don't always take time for during a busy week. I've also realized how powerful it is to talk with others about teaching, through real, ongoing conversations.

By looking closely at my own lessons and talking them through with someone else, I've deepened my understanding, not just of the topic I started with, but of my whole teaching approach. I'm learning how to adapt and how to be more intentional in what I do.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

Even though I started this process to improve one small part of my teaching, it's become something more. It's reminded me that being a good teacher isn't about having all the answers, it's about being open to learning, staying

curious, and being willing to change. I'm learning to challenge my own assumptions and to look at my routines with fresh eyes.

Why it matters

Signature pedagogies matter because they fundamentally shape how teachers become professionals—not only through what they learn, but through how they learn. By identifying and purposefully applying these pedagogies, the PhysEd-Academy Framework empowers teacher educators to move beyond fragmented methods toward a cohesive, reflective, and evidence-informed approach to teacher learning and development.

Importantly, the PhysEd-Academy framework does not prescribe a single way to teach teachers. Instead, it identifies a set of pedagogical forms that are flexible, relational, and deeply tied to authentic learning. These signature pedagogies are adaptable across national contexts, educational levels, and institutional cultures. They offer a common language and conceptual foundation that can guide innovation in teacher education globally.

Moreover, when used alongside 1. Collective Action methodologies (Strand 1 of the PhysEd-Academy Framework), these pedagogies help create professional learning ecosystems where teachers are positioned not as passive recipients of knowledge but as active contributors to educational reform. They enable the development of teaching cultures that are reflective, evidence-informed, and purpose-driven.

Transferability and Sustainability

While the *PhysEd-Academy Framework* is rooted in physical education, its principles and methods are broadly transferable to other subject areas and teacher education contexts. The core ideas—collective action, reflective practice, and the purposeful use of signature pedagogies—are not discipline-specific; they speak to the universal challenges of preparing teachers for complexity, diversity, and change.

Transferability is enabled through:

- A flexible framework adaptable to local, regional, and national education systems;
- Cross-cutting pedagogical principles grounded in inquiry, collaboration, and inclusivity;
- Tools and practices that can be scaled and contextualized by diverse educational actors.

Sustainability is ensured by:

- Embedding innovation within existing institutions through long-term partnerships;
- Empowering teachers as agents of change through professional learning;
- Supporting ongoing dialogue and mutual learning through international networks.

In a world where teacher education must be both adaptive and grounded, the *PhysEd-Academy Framework* offers a robust foundation for meaningful and lasting change—within physical education and well beyond.

Annex 1

CASE 2: Learning Through Reflecting on your Own Teaching Stories

I'm a very committed teacher educator with almost 20 years of experience. For me teaching is about being honest and transparent, being knowledgeable and prepared. It is about creating a space for your students to learn and grow as persons. My evolving teaching philosophy is informed by one core statement: "I want to educate critical, adaptative and reflective physical education teachers". One key aspect to enact this philosophy is by challenging preservice teachers (PSTs) to be critical and reflective with their own teaching stories.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Overall, PSTs are asked to "look back" on their previous teaching experiences, "scan" for potential scenarios where some ism-s¹ were present, "make sense" and reflect on those scenarios, and "propose" socially just alternatives (e.g., update teaching resources, groupings, etc.). This reflective process aimed to help them identify potential areas for improvement and deepen their understanding of how to integrate social justice principles into their teaching. PSTs engaged with and reflected on their school placement stories, and co-created case studies based on those lived experiences. Some visual case studies are used and shared with PSTs to provoke and prompt this thinking process. [All of them can be accessed here.](#)

What does this help they learn? (Deep Structure)

Strategies such as the "look back approach" and self-reflection on past actions or designs enhance PSTs' awareness and increase their ability to identify social injustices that they had previously overlooked. PSTs developed the ability to think critically and reflexively and to be sensitive to their own and others' lived experiences as they both challenge and develop their beliefs about teaching and learning. That was done in the weekly discussions as part of the small learning communities.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

Autobiographical pedagogies (e.g. "look back approach"), highlights the necessity of being accompanied by pedagogies of care, as it deals with sensitive topics where PSTs learn to analyse themselves and reshape their identities by modifying past habits (some of them quite strongly and unconsciously ingrained). PSTs emphasised how these pedagogies have challenged their own beliefs about how they taught and how they should have taught to include all learners. They also stressed that such reflections are only possible when the pedagogy is implemented with a foundation of care. As a teacher educator, I need to be able to create that safe and democratic space where the PSTs, feel respected and empowered to be self-critical and learn from their own teaching stories

CASE 3: Developing a Vision – what’s my philosophy?

As a teacher educator, I together with my colleagues create tasks (can be part of a written exam) where we want the students to reason about their future profession. For example, in one course/module (in the fourth year of five) the task is that the students should create their own philosophy for how to implement or work with the field *Movement and dance*.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

In the example, the task is for the students to reflect and discuss how they in their future profession as a PE-teacher want to integrate and work with *Movement and Dance* with their students. They are to use all experiences throughout the whole PETE program including those they may have gained if they had the opportunity to teach dance within the school-placement periods. Thereby they get a chance to look back and reflect on how *Movement and Dance* have been presented within the program, what forms of dance they have met (cultural, creative and training) and how the teachers have created learning environments for them as students but also for them as student teachers.

The progression of the exam is that the students submit their own text but will have a chance to discuss it in a smaller group (about 5-6 students). Everyone in the group reads the texts, but each one also gets assigned one text to read as a “critical friend”. In the seminar, the critical friend presents the text for the group and then leads a conversation with the author asking (critical) questions to give the author a chance to elaborate around the text. After the conversation, the other students are also invited to pose questions and finally the teacher wraps it up, often by adding something that the student needs to change with the text in order to pass.

What does this help the student to learn? (Deep Structure)

By looking back, the PETE-students get a chance to see and reflect on their own progression over the four years that they have been studying, both when it comes to their own movement ability but also and possibly even greater how they have developed as teachers. They are “forced” to reflect upon the learning activities – *what happened* – their experiences – *how did it feel* – and in conclusion – *what have I learnt*. Hopefully, they have developed insights on what kind of knowledge *Movement and Dance* can support but also how they can create these learning arenas as future teachers. These reflections, together with insights from reviewing the literature, and the discussions in class will be a good base for forming their own philosophy of (in this case) *Movement and Dance*.

What have the students learned about their underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

With this assignment, the students have to take a stand on Why, What and How to teach concerning *Movement and Dance*. Many students enter the program with either bad experiences from their own time in school or preconceived notions of what dance is. With this task, together with the

practical learning activities, they have the chance to elaborate around what dance could be and, most important, what dance can become.

CASE 4: Staging a situation from my school-placement - Using Vignettes/Storytelling

As a part of a concluding seminar in the second (of three) school placements course, the students are asked to elaborate on a specific situation that has happened during the time in secondary school. The topic of the task is "conflicts" and how to deal with them.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

At the seminar, the students are divided into smaller groups where they are given some time to tell their fellow students about the situations and how they were handled by the student/teacher (the supervisor/pupils) or the school. Then the group are to choose one or possibly merge two stories together and prepare a small scene where they portray the situation. All groups perform their small scenes with a following discussion around ways to handle conflicts and if they actual situation could have been handled differently.

What does this help students to learn? (Deep Structure)

Using roleplay as a didactical tool is quite efficient in order to open up for discussions but also for the student themselves to relive the situations. This is a multilayered exercise where they are both acting as parts of the conflict but also reflecting about ways to handle different situations. To prepare future teachers about have to handle and solve conflicts is a well-known problem within (PE)TE, not least because conflicts tend to be contextual. This chance of acting out different situations give students a hunch though and since it is lived experiences, they will most likely be emotionally involved.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

In the case of conflicts there might not be one way to handling them, but several. This exercise may provoke the students into reflecting about different types of courses of action. As mentioned above, it is difficult to teach about conflicts, one has to experience them to be prepared, but this exercise gives the students a chance to: i) feel the actual situation (getting emotionally involved), ii) act the course of action and with this develop tools in how to handle certain situations, or at least get the frames to work with.

CASE 5: Living the Curriculum / Modelling

The goal was to help future Primary Education Physical Education teachers see the subject through a "new lens", moving them from teacher-centered to student-centered teaching.

Based on this idea, we (Teacher Educators) designed our classes at the university to make the pre-service teachers "live the curriculum", in particular models-based practice, and produce a shift through a "vivid" experience.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Before coming to class, pre-service teachers were asked to read an article on the topic selected (e.g, cooperative learning). In the same line, they were asked to do a search on internet and upload a link of a "source" related to the topic (webpage, video, article...) to the university on-line campus. The last task before coming to class was to review the class notes uploaded by the Teacher Educator to the university on-line campus.

In the "theory" class, all the previously mentioned resources were reviewed and the information discussed to obtain deeper knowledge on the topic.

In the "practice" class, the teacher led a session on the topic selected for the pre-service teachers to experience it as students. In the final step, the pre-service teachers were asked to develop a practical session and conduct it using their classmates as students.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

It helped me (Educator) learn how my students dealt with new ideas and concepts, when trying to make a shift from competitive teacher-centred contexts to cooperative student-centred ones.

I believe that it helped my students (pre-service Primary Education Physical Education teachers) integrate information on a "new way of teaching" progressively. First, acquiring knowledge on the topic through searches and discussions. Second, experience it as Primary Education students. Third and final, design their own lesson and test it with their fellow classmates.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

I (Teacher Educator) have learned that it is not easy to change the views of pre-service teachers with a "fixed" idea of what a physical education class should look like in Primary Education. For some this shift is fast, while others take more time. You need to be patient and provide lots of feedback.

However, I truly believe that "living the curriculum" (at least the way it was conducted), it is a framework capable of transforming pre-service teachers' views and help them see physical education "through a new lens". It works!!!

CASE 6: Independent Teaching in School Placement - Linking Theory with Practice in Physical Education

This case study draws from my experience working with third-year pre-service teachers (PSTs) enrolled in a Physical Education Teacher Education (PETE) program, during the final stage of their school placement in primary education settings. At this point, PSTs have already completed earlier phases of observation and assisted teaching, and are now transitioning into the most demanding phase: Independent Teaching. In this stage, each PST is allocated to teach full physical education (PE) lessons independently across different age groups in primary schools. The experience is intentionally designed to allow PSTs to embody the professional role of a teacher, navigate real classroom challenges, and critically apply the pedagogical knowledge they have developed throughout their academic journey.

How does this look in practice? (Surface structure)

PSTs independently lead PE lessons for children aged 6-10, aligning content with the curriculum and student developmental levels. They manage all aspects of the lesson - from planning and organization to instruction, behaviour management, and safety, while adapting to real-world challenges (e.g., space, student diversity, weather). Throughout the process, peer PSTs are invited to observe lessons and offer structured feedback, which complements the formal feedback provided by mentors and university supervisors and self-reflection from teaching experience. This final stage of placement is designed to mirror the real-life work PSTs will encounter in their future careers. It requires them to move beyond their comfort zone, to take full ownership of their teaching, and to integrate theoretical knowledge with practical decision-making in a dynamic school setting.

What does this help students learn? (Deep experience)

The Independent Teaching stage of school placement enables PSTs to learn how to teach, not just what to teach, allowing authentic classroom experiences. PSTs gain key competencies such as lesson design, adaptation for diverse learners, real-time instructional decisions, movement-based lessons. They learn to reflect on student engagement and learning outcome and use feedback from mentors, teacher educators, and peers to refine their teaching practice; experience the responsibility and autonomy of leading a class and building confidence and professional identity. Importantly, the school placement helps students to connect theory to practice as strategies discussed in lectures (e.g., differentiation, scaffolding, inclusive teaching) become tools they actively test and revise in their own teaching.

What underlying values do students learn? (Implicit Structure)

This final stage of school placement is a transformative moment in PETE as provides PSTs transition from learners to practitioners, navigating the real-world complexities of teaching PE in primary schools. PSTs internalize values such as professionalism, responsibility, and ethical practice. They embrace a growth mindset by viewing mistakes as learning opportunities and value collaboration and feedback. Through self-reflection and mentoring, PST`s begin to see themselves as committed, reflective professionals ready for lifelong learning.

CASE 7: Peer Teaching for Developing Assessment Literacy in PE

As a teacher educator, I teach various didactical courses within our physical education teacher education (PETE) programme. One of the key aims across these courses is to prepare pre-service teachers to design, deliver, and evaluate learning in physical education, with a strong foundation in *assessment literacy*. Among the diverse pedagogical approaches I use, peer teaching stands out as one of the most valuable.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Pre-service teachers work in groups to plan, design, and deliver mini-units. This includes developing original rating scales for motor tasks, constructing theoretical tests, and designing learning sequences with integrated assessment strategies. For every unit, each group presents their work to peers, who then give oral feedback using teacher-facilitated prompts. This peer exchange occurs in a structured setting where pre-service teachers assume dual roles: as "teachers" delivering content and as "learners" responding, critiquing, and offering constructive feedback. To enhance authenticity, pre-service teachers also evaluate video-based motor tasks individually using various AoL methods (e.g., analytical, weighted), followed by group discussions.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

Peer teaching enables pre-service teachers to transfer theoretical knowledge into practical pedagogical actions. This experience strengthens their understanding of how assessment functions in real educational settings. The process of giving and receiving feedback heightens their awareness of assessment principles and pushes them to consider teaching from multiple perspectives—teacher, peer, and learner. Over time, pre-service teachers gain confidence not just in content knowledge, but in how to communicate, justify, and reflect on that knowledge through teaching interactions. They also begin to question their assumptions about assessment and recognize its complexity.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

By allowing pre-service teachers to co-construct knowledge and critically engage with each other's teaching practices, peer teaching fosters professional dialogue, mutual responsibility, and deeper pedagogical insight. Moreover, it offers pre-service teachers opportunities to practice teaching and engage critically with the learning process—developing not only their instructional skills but also their reflective, collaborative, and assessment competencies, as well as the openness,

empathy, and inquiry that define effective educators. However, building a reflective and collaborative culture takes time and guidance.

CASE 8: Learning With and From One Another

In the department where I work, learning with and from one another has been used a common pedagogical approach and the foundation of powerful and meaningful educational experiences for preservice teachers (PSTs) but also for us, teacher educators. When I first came in, I indeed bought into the idea of working in small learning communities and tweaked it a bit to make this learning together piece, stronger.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

Every week, PSTs are grouped in small teams (4-5) and are allocated a relevant resource to engage with (e.g., research paper, podcast, blog post) related to the content being taught every week (e.g., culturally relevant pedagogies). Before coming to class, each PST had to complete a weekly submission (e.g., answering specific questions like 'share something from that resource that resonates with your teaching philosophy, in 50-100 words'). Once in class, the weekly submission was first discussed within the small teams, and then within the large class.

What does this help they learn? (Deep Structure)

By working with diverse resources in small teams and responding to focused reflective prompts, PSTs develop habits of critical thinking. The process of discussing their reflections in small teams and then with the whole class fosters collaborative learning (e.g., learning with and from) and the ability to articulate and refine their ideas through dialogue. It also encourages them to apply theoretical concepts to practical teaching contexts, recognise multiple perspectives, and begin to see themselves as part of a professional learning community.

What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience? (Implicit Structure)

This experience strongly aligns with my deep beliefs and values on dialogue, critical reflection, and the creation of spaces where PSTs can safely articulate and discuss ideas and develop their own identities as teachers. Facilitating these weekly engagements has reaffirmed my commitment to democratic, relational and participatory approaches to teacher education, where learning is co-constructed and shaped by diverse voices. It has also highlighted my belief in modelling some practices I hope PSTs will take into their future classrooms.

CASE 9: Learning Through Adaptation – Rethinking How I Teach Future PE Teachers

As a teacher educator, every year, I teach a course on model-based practice in our PETE program. In this course, students are required to work in small groups to select one instructional model—such as Sport Education, Cooperative Learning, or Teaching Personal and Social Responsibility—and develop a theoretical presentation and a practical lesson demonstration based on that model. Over the years, I noticed that each group of students came with different experiences, expectations, and confidence levels, while I kept the course structure mostly the same. To address this challenge, I decided to use a framework called Learning Through Action to revise the course design based on student feedback.

What does this look like in practice? (Surface Structure)

At the end of each semester, I collected open-ended reflections from pre-service teachers about their experiences with the group project. I carefully analyzed their feedback to see what worked well, what didn't, and what could be improved. Based on this analysis, I made iterative adjustments for the next cohort's experience. For example:

- When students expressed feeling unprepared for the practical session, I implemented structured peer-teaching sessions where they could practice their lesson plans and receive constructive feedback before presenting.
- When students reported that some group members weren't contributing equally, I created specific roles for each team member and made individual accountability clear.
- When students requested more realistic contexts, I incorporated short field visits and peer observations during teaching practice.

Each version of the course became a living document, constantly shaped by the insights gained from my previous students.

What does this help me learn? (Deep Structure)

This process has helped me understand that learning to teach is not a linear journey. By treating each class as a unique context and paying close attention to student feedback, I have developed a deeper understanding of how model-based instruction is received and interpreted by learners. I now see curriculum planning as a teamwork effort. I do not impose my plan on students; instead, we work on it together. The Learning Through Action framework has shown me that each semester is a cycle of planning, teaching, reflecting, and revising, with students involved at every step.

**What have I learned about my underlying values through this experience?
(Implicit Structure)**

This journey has strengthened my belief in being responsive, reflective, and respectful. I used to think of the curriculum was fixed; now, I see it as a flexible practice that can adapt to changing needs.

This experience has also made me more open and honest as a teacher educator. By welcoming feedback and showing that I am also learning and growing, I have created a more open and engaging learning environment. My students now see reflective practice not only as something I teach but also as something I practice myself.

